

DESIGN, FABRICATION, AND TEST OF A COMPOSITE SANDWICH PANEL COMPONENT FOR AIRFRAME PRIMARY STRUCTURAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development of a composite honeycomb stiffened panel with secondarily bonded composite frames representative of a highly loaded airframe wing or fuselage structure. Topics discussed include the design philosophy, loads, structural analysis, fabrication methods, structural test fixturing, and test results. The panel is 100 cm (40 in.) long by 75 cm (30 in.) wide with 2 secondarily bonded 10 cm (4 in.) deep frames. Bays between frames are stiffened with 9.5 mm (0.375 in.) thick non metallic honeycomb core with thin IM7/8551-7A facesheets. The panel was loaded in combined axial compression and shear until failure. Correlation between NASTRAN analysis and observed failure modes are evaluated.

INTRODUCTION

Although honeycomb sandwich structures have been flying for years on military and commercial aircraft, few have found their way into primary structural applications. Potential weight savings associated with these structures are often negated by design and maintainability concerns. Frequent use of potting in joint areas, moisture ingress into the core after impact, and difficulty of repair have prevented the emergence of sandwich construction as a common approach to primary airframe structure. Notable exceptions to this general statement are the B-58 Hustler (aluminum sandwich skin panels), the XB-70 bomber (steel sandwich skin panels), and more recently the Voyager and Beech Starship (composite sandwich panels). The FAA certified Starship airframe (Reference 1) used composite sandwich over nearly the entire structure for the skin panels, approaching a true monocoque design. The intention of our study was to scale the loads up from composite general aviation aircraft to levels more representative of primary load carrying skin panels on a fighter or transport airframe, while keeping the weight low through attention to design details.

A trade study was conducted to compare the weight of three composite skin panel design concepts: 1) a stiffened solid laminate, 2) a stiffened syncore sandwich panel, and 3) a thick honeycomb sandwich panel. Typical cross sections for the three panels are shown in Figure 1. The syncore (Reference 2) and solid laminate panels were allowed to buckle at limit load (post-buckling designs) while the honeycomb version was designed for no buckling at ultimate load. The panel dimensions in each case were 75 cm (30 in.) by 100 cm (40 in.) with ultimate combined loads of 157.6 kN/m (900 lb/in) in axial compression and 78.8 kN/m (450 lb/in) shear. Results of this study showed a weight savings of 17% for the honeycomb version versus the stiffened laminate panel, and 13% for the syncore version. The honeycomb stiffened version was selected for fabrication and structural test based on these results.

DESIGN AND FABRICATION

The honeycomb sandwich panel was designed with 6 ply (0.75 mm) IM8/8551-7A toughened epoxy facesheets over 9.5 mm (0.375 in.) thick HRH-327 honeycomb core. The core ramped down to provide a solid land areas for the two frames and bolted load introduction around the periphery. The frame land area and associated design details are shown schematically in Figure 2. A Rohacell foam core detail was machined for the ramped transition, and FM 404 foaming adhesive provided the core splice between the foam and honeycomb cores. Both facesheet laminates doubled in thickness to 12 plies (1.5 mm) in the ramped region, and additional plies were added beneath the frame for a total thickness of 3.55 mm (0.140 in.).

The entire sandwich skin assembly was co-cured with the honeycomb core details in place using a non-autoclave curing process which incorporates a double vacuum. A hard outer shell (which does not come in contact with the part) was placed over the flat tool plate to hold the outer vacuum, and a standard bagging procedure was used for the inner vacuum. When the air is evacuated from both the inner bag and the outer chamber, it allows vacuum to be applied to the part *with no net pressure applied*. This allows the volatiles to out-gas during heat up without local bubbles or pockets forming due to the bag pressure. After the volatiles have been bled off, the vacuum is released from the outer chamber, and the part is cured using atmospheric pressure (100 kPa) from the inner bag. The cured skin panel was inspected using pulse echo ultrasonic C-scan methods, and no inherent porosity was observed. The frame web laminate was fabricated using 16 plies (2.1 mm) of unidirectional IM8/8551-7A prepreg, and was cured using a conventional autoclave cure cycle.

The cured skin and frame details were joined together using a co-bonding process. Co-bonding in this case means that prepreg angle plies were laid in place uncured against the precured skin and frame details with a layer of FM300 film adhesive to form the bond line. Unidirectional filler plies were used in the corners to form a smooth joint radius. A schematic of the co-bonded joint area is shown in Figure 3. The frame web was held in place during the cure by a tooling fixture, and the assembly was transferred to the autoclave to cure the joint. The fabrication process was successful, and a cross section of the resulting geometry is shown in Figure 4.

The completed panel is shown in Figure 5. The frames run the entire length of the panel, to facilitate direct attachment to the end plates on the loading fixture for structural test. The core stiffened areas can be observed in the Figure, with one large central honeycomb bay, and two smaller outboard regions.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Two finite element models were created in support of the structural test and failure mode prediction for the panel. The first was a two dimensional model of the local ramp detail geometry at the core close-out, and the second was a three dimensional model of the entire panel. The results of the local ramp model were used to calculate ramp stiffness inputs for the larger model of the panel assembly. These inputs were critical to determining the load distribution between the honeycomb stiffened areas and the built up land areas beneath the frames.

The mesh geometry, element numbers, and constraints for the local ramp model are shown in Figure 6. Compressive forces were applied via rigid bar elements connected across the sandwich facesheets shown at the left side of the figure. These forces created equal displacement of both facesheets at these nodes. The compressive forces were reacted by translational and rotational constraints at nodes in the solid land area corresponding to the location of the retaining bolts.

Because the centroid of the load changes over the length of the ramp detail, local bending and transverse forces are created due to the eccentric loading. These forces are displayed graphically in Figure 7, which shows stress contours through the thickness of the core due to ultimate compressive loads of 157.6 kN/m (900 lb/in). The vertical dimension of the ramp has been doubled in this plot to improve clarity of the contours, the actual model was not changed. Ramping the core creates a flatwise tensile stress of 1450 kPa (210 psi) near the top of the ramp, and a crushing stress of 620 kPa (90 psi) near the bottom of the ramp.

The corresponding in-plane facesheet strain contours during ultimate compression loading are shown in Figure 8. The strain values shown have been multiplied by a factor of 1000 for clarity. The obvious trend displayed by the facesheet strains is that nearly all the load stays in the flat outer mold line facesheet. An attempt was made during the design phase to compensate for the eccentricity of the ramp by doubling the thickness of both faces over the ramp, and dropping them off over a distance of 13 mm (0.50 in) to the nominal 6 ply thickness. The model results indicate that a better approach is to increase the thickness of the flat facesheet only, since the additional material in the ramped facesheet does not participate in carrying axial load. The maximum laminate strains in the outer facesheet were 27,000 micro m/m, nearly double the unnotched allowable. Note that this model assumed that all of the load was being reacted by the sandwich panels, and did not account for the frame land areas. The larger 3 dimensional model of the assembly was required to predict the actual expected panel load distribution and failure modes.

Since the panel is symmetric about both centerlines, a 1/4 panel model was built with symmetry constraints at both panel centerlines. A planview of the model is shown in Figure 9. This stiffness model was used to predict the strain distribution in the panel during structural test. Results also showed that the frame did not participate in carrying any significant axial load unless the load was applied directly to the frame ends (it was too deep for the load to shear in from the plane of the sandwich skin panel). Based on these results, the test fixturing was fitted with angle brackets to apply loads directly to the frame webs, and critical strain gage locations were identified in preparation for structural test.

STRUCTURAL TEST

The combined loading test fixture at Northrop uses a torque box consisting of three panels which are bolted together via fiberglass angles along their long edges to form a triangular "torque tube". This tube is mounted between two massive end plates. One end plate is fixed and forms the "brick wall" for the fixture. The other endplate is mounted on a bearing, and attached to large hydraulic load cylinders. Certain cylinders cause the plate to translate, resulting in axial compression or tension, while other cylinders cause the plate to rotate, resulting in torsional shear on the test section. By combining the translation and rotation, any combination of biaxial loading may be applied to the test section. Typically, two of the three panels in the test box are fiberglass dummy panels (provide stability, but carry nominal load) while the third panel is the test component.

A photo of the sandwich panel assembly mounted in the Northrop combined loading fixture is shown in Figure 10. The dummy panels are hidden behind the test panel, but the end plates are visible at the left and right sides. The restraining bolts are 6.35 mm (0.25 in.) diameter steel bolts mounted at 25.4 mm (1.0 in.) pitch around the entire periphery of the panel. The bolt holes for the frame attachment had not been match drilled yet when this photo was taken. The panel was subjected to 4 impacts representing barely visible and clearly visible damage (Reference 3) using a 12.7 mm (0.50 in.) diameter falling weight impactor prior to mounting in the test fixture. The first three impacts were located in the central bay area on the six ply facesheet with impact energies of 5.42, 5.42, and 8.13 N-m. The fourth impact was located on the frame land area with an impact energy of 20.3 N-m. A total of ten strain gages were mounted and monitored during the test.

The strain data taken during the test correlated to within 10% with the finite element model predictions. Gages in the ramp area showed behavior similar to the results from the local ramp model, while a second set of gages at the mid span showed nearly uniform loading between the facesheets. These data display the ability of the honeycomb sandwich to redistribute loads between the facesheets via shear load transfer through the core. The load becomes balanced at a distance away from the ramped region of five to ten times the core thickness, depending on the shear stiffness of the core.

The panel failed under combined loading, at 145% of design ultimate load. Failure occurred at an axial running load of 228.4 kN/m (1305 lb/in), and shear of 114.2 kN/m (652 lb/in). The maximum recorded strain was 2950 micro m/m. Failure occurred in the ramped core area, and propagated across the panel and through the bolt line as shown in Figure 11. Failure initiation was

a compressive failure of the facesheet laminate under the ramped area due to dissimilar loading between the two facesheets. A secondary failure observed was disbonding of the frame co-bond angles from the skin subsequent to initial panel failure. No failure was observed in the impacted regions of the panel.

REFERENCES

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2. Clark, J., "Graphite Reinforced Syntactic Film Mini-Sandwich Structure", Presented at the 35th International SAMPE Symposium, April 2-5, 1990
3. Bohner, R., Palm, T., "Preliminary Design and Structural Concept Trade Studies for Ultralightweight Structures", Air Force Contract F33615-88-C-3202, Final Technical Report, July 1990.

Figure 1. Panel Concepts for Weight Trade Study

Figure 2. Sandwich Component Ramp Details

Figure 3. Co-Bond Frame Attachment Diagram

Figure 4. Cross Section of Actual Co-Bonded Frame Assembly

Figure 5. Completed Sandwich Stiffened Test Article

Figure 6. Finite Element Model Geometry for Local Ramp Detail

Figure 7. Core Tensile and Crushing Stresses at Ramp due to Eccentricity

Figure 8. Facesheet Axial Compression Strain Contour

Figure 9. Finite Element Geometry for Quarter Symmetry Model.

Figure 10. Sandwich Component Mounted in Combined Loading Fixture

Figure 11. Initial Failure in Ramped Region of Sandwich Component